

THE MAHA BODHI

Special Issue on 100 Years Celebration of
Sri Dharmarajika Chaitya Vihara

2564 B.E. • Vol.128 • December 2020 • ISSN: 0025 0406

MAHA BODHI SOCIETY OF INDIA

Headquarters, Kolkata • www.mbsiindia.org

THE MAHA BODHI

Founded by Bodhisattva Anagariaka Dharmapala

“Go Ye, O Bhikkhus, and wander forth for the gain of the many, for the welfare of the many, in compassion for the world, for the good, for the gain, for the welfare of gods and men. Proclaim, O Bhikkhus, the Doctrine glorious, preach ye a life of holiness, perfect and pure.

- Mahavagga, Vinaya Pitaka

2564 B.E.

Vol. 128

December 2020

“Countless times I took birth in *Samsāra*, all the time incessantly running (towards the death). In search of the Builder of this house I have been taking in misery again and again. O builder of the house! You are now seen, You can’t build the house again. All the rafters and the central pole (the building materials of the house) are shattered. The mind is free from all the (*bhava*) *Saṅkhāra*. The craving free stage attained”

-Words of the Buddha on attaining *Sammā Sambodhi*

MAHA BODHI SOCIETY OF INDIA

Sri Dharmarajika Chetiya Vihara

Headquarters : 4A, Bankim Chatterjee Street,
Kolkata 700 073, India, Tel : 033 2241 5214

Email : mbsihq@gmail.com / mbsi.ipmd@gmail.com

Website: www.mbsiindia.org

Published by:

Maha Bodhi Society of India,
4A, Bankim Chatterjee Street,
Kolkata 700 073.

Tele: 033-2241 5214

Email: mbsihq@gmail.com

mbsi.ipmd@gmail.com

Editor-in-Chief

Most. Ven. P. Seewalee Maha Thero

Editorial Board

Hemendu Bikash Chowdhury

Prof. Saswati Mutsuddy

Dr. Ujjwal Kumar

Editor

Prof. (Dr.) Bimalendra Kumar

Note: Contributors of the articles are solely responsible for contents in the same.

Printed at

Rohini Nandan

19/2, Radhanath Mallick Lane

Kolkata 700 012, Mob: 9231508276

Email : rohininandanpub@gmail.com

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BOOK REVIEW

Name of the Book : *Relations in Abhidhamma Philosophy*

Author : Bimalendra Kumar

ISBN : 978-81-7854-383-3 Pages: 186

First Edition: 2020

Price: ₹ 550 (Hardcover)

Publisher: Eastern Book Linkers, 5825, New Chandrawal,
Jawahar Nagar, Delhi - 110007

Reviewed by : Prof. Ramesh Prasad, Dean, Faculty of Śramaṇa Vidyā, Head - Deptt. of Pāli & Theravāda, Sampurnanand Sanskrit University, Varanasi, E-mail : rprasadpali@gmail.com

Knowing the **relation** rightly plays an important role to live the life happily. Lord *Buddha* devoted his whole life to make the people understand the relation that how to behave with each other so that the peace and harmony could exist in the society.

Prof. Bimalendra Kumar, Head, Department of Pali and Buddhist Studies, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi (U.P.) has truly tried to present the 24 types of relation, i.e., *Paccayas* through *Abhidhamma Philosophy*. His book named *Relations in Abhidhamma Philosophy*, mainly based on *Paṭṭhānappakarāṇa*, contains seven chapters in which theory of relations have been vividly discussed.

Man without mind (*Nāma*) is corpse and there are no words for a man without matter (*Rūpa*). Mind is conscious and the matter is devoid of consciousness (*Citta*) and psychic factors (*Cetasika*). Both are opposite to each other in their nature but there remains mutual understanding as well as harmonious functioning in them. This mutual relation of mind and matter has been interpreted in the first chapter.

In the second chapter, Dr. Kumar has genuinely attempted to discuss the analytical exposition of the 24 types of relation with definition and examples as appeared in the *Paṭṭhānappakarāṇa* and its commentary. Chapter number 3 has been separately created to explain the relations of mind and matter. How *Pañcadvārāvīthi* and *Manodvārāvīthi* cognise their respective objects with the help of theory of relation has been explained briefly from page numbers 119 to 125 in the 4th chapter of the book.

The law of dependant origination is the marvellous discovery of the *Buddha* where cause and effect relation has been established. The author has explained this law of dependant origination through the theory of relations in the 5th chapter.

In addition to *Theravāda* tradition the author has also manifested the theory of relations as in *Sarvāstivāda Abhidharma* tradition. Other aspects related to the importance of human relation such as psychological life, ethical life, religious life, social behaviour and some other philosophical ideals i.e. four noble truths, noble eight-fold path, theory of dependent origination, theory of action, theory of resultant, theory of rebirth have been incorporated in the last chapter of the book.

The said book is the extension of his previous book named "*Theory of Relations in Buddhist Philosophy*", which was published by Eastern Book Linkers, Delhi in 1988. While writing the Foreword of his earlier book Prof. Mahesh Tiwari, Former head, Department of Buddhist studies,

University of Delhi, Delhi said – “ He has made a commendable contribution in the field of early Buddhist Philosophy and opened the door for entering into the vast literature of Abhidhammic lore for the benefit of many, having academic and spiritual interest ”¹. Reviewing the author’s first book i.e. Theory of relations in Buddhist philosophy, Prof. G. C. Pandey wrote – “The present work gives a clear and summary description of the Abhidhammic theory and is therefore to be commended as an introductory account for students and scholars not familiar with Abhidharma”². This Book Review was published in The Indian Historical Review, (Ed.) Vivekanand Jha, Volume XVII, Number 1-2, July 1990 & January 1991, Motilal Banarasidass, Delhi, pp. 226 – 227. Above mentioned Foreword and Book Review have been given a place in this book from page numbers xix to xxii.

The two eminent Buddhist scholars, Prof. Charles Willemen, Rector, International Buddhist College, Thailand and Prof. G. A. Somaratne, Centre of Buddhist Studies, The University of Hong Kong, thoroughly went through this book and admired it in their Forewords. Commending the book Prof. Charles Willemen wrote – “ It is quite rewarding to read this book, and in the future this work will be a useful reference work.”³ Throwing light on the importance of the book Prof. G. A. Somratane commented - “Through my quick reading into this book made me amazed to identify how brilliantly Prof. Bimalendra Kumar articulates the Theravāda theory of relations between mind and matter in an easy to understand language, clarifying and interpreting the meanings of almost all the *Abidhamma* terms that require for understanding the subtle nuances of this profound subject . As I see, the work is truly an excellent piece produced on the *Theravāda Abhidhamma* in recent history.”⁴

The author starts the book by dedicating it to Late Prof. Ram Shankar Tripathy. Former Head, Department of Bauddha Darśana and Former Dean, Faculty of Śramaṇa Vidyā, Sampurnanand Sanskrit University, Varanasi. Dr. Kumar has very thoughtfully added a list of abbreviations before the content to help out the reader. He ends the book with Bibliography and Index at the last.

He has put together almost all technical terms in the index but some terms and page numbers got mismatched. For example – the words like *Arahanta*, *Arahata-phalacitta* are not present at their given page numbers. Though *Parikkhāra-hāra* is present on page number 8 but it is written *Parikkāra-hāra* in the index which is wrong and the word is not present at all on page number 14. The diacritical mark is not properly used in some words such as *Anūṭīkā* (page no. 74), *Aññātavindriyam* (page no. 75), the correct words are *Anuṭīkā*, *Aññātāvindriyam*. Three forewords, one book review and preface are not in the correct order. I hope these mistakes will be sorted out in the next edition by the author.

The print quality of this book is good and its getup is quite attractive. The brief introduction of the book on the front flap and about the author on the back flap are quite impressive. The language is simple and its content is easy to understand. This book is very useful for Buddhist scholars especially Abhidhamma lovers. The author has done a great contribution by fulfilling the requirements of *Abhidhammic* book in English language related to *Paccayas*. I heartily congratulate Prof. Bimalendra Kumar jee for sharing his precious knowledge to us.

End notes

1. Bimalendra Kumar, *Relations in Abhidhamma Philosophy*, Eastern Book Linkers, Delhi, 2020, p. xxii
2. Ibid. p. xix
3. Ibid. p. ix
4. Ibid. p. xvii